

ADDENDUM TO THE OPHONE MANIFESTO: UPDATED LEGAL NOTICE

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This document is a legal addendum to the oPhone Manifesto (DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.20380296](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20380296)), originally published on 26 May 2026.

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The original text of the oPhone Manifesto remains unchanged and continues to serve as Prior Art. This addendum updates the licensing terms governing the use, modification, and distribution of the oPhone Manifesto.

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This addendum is effective immediately. It does not alter the status of the oPhone Manifesto as Prior Art. In the event of any inconsistency between this addendum and the original license text within the oPhone Manifesto file, this addendum shall prevail.

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